

Physico-Chemical Studies of Copper (II)-Phthalic Acid System.

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Stability constants of copper(II)-phthalic acid complexes were determined potentiometrically at 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 M ionic strengths in the aqueous medium at 30°. Ionic strength data was utilised to test the applicability of Brönsted equation and modified Debye-Hückel equation to the reaction equilibrium. The mean distance of approach 'a' between copper(II) ion and the ligand was evaluated as 6Å. If H₂L is ligand, 1 : 1 complexation is shown to be occurring by $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{HL}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuL} + \text{H}^+$ and not by $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuHL}^+ + \text{H}^+$ reaction. The thermodynamic stability constants pK_1^0 , pK_2^0 and $\log K_1^0$ at zero ionic strength are also determined.

The influence of the solvent was studied by evaluating stability constants in 20%, 40%, 60%, and 80% dioxane-water mixtures at 30° and 0.1 M ionic strength in addition to the study in aqueous medium as mentioned earlier.

PK values of phthalic acid were determined by many workers¹⁻⁴ but the agreement between these values is poor. Copper complex of phthalic acid was studied by Yamasaki *et al.*¹ and Ghosh and Nair⁵ only at 0.1M ionic strength. However, a detailed study of complexes considering manifold aspects is still lacking. The present work deals with a systematic study of stability constants of Cu(II)-phthalic acid system, (i) in the aqueous medium of various ionic strengths and (ii) in the dioxane-water mixtures of different compositions. The former study helps in understanding the mechanism of the reaction and the latter gives information about the influence of dielectric constant on the stability constants.

Experimental

Materials: Phthalic acid, sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid were of Analytical Reagent grade obtained from E. Merck. Copper perchlorate was prepared by the standard method and the concentration of Cu(II) in the aqueous solution was estimated by EDTA titration using Schwarzenbach's method⁶. All solutions were prepared in the double distilled water. Dioxane obtained from B.D.H. was purified by the method given by Vogel⁷. Fresh solutions of all the reagents were used for different measurements.

Apparatus: Beckman model H-2 pH meter giving an accuracy of ± 0.02 pH unit was used for the pH measurements. pH meter was calibrated by the solutions of buffer tablets at pH 4.01 and 9.11 at 30°. Ultrathermostat with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.02^\circ$ was used to maintain the temperature of titration assembly at 30°.

Calvin-Bjerrum titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations of carbonate free solutions of (i) free HClO₄, (ii) free HClO₄ +

phthalic acid, (iii) free HClO₄ + phthalic acid + copper ion, and (iv) free HClO₄ + copper perchlorate against standard NaOH solution from a microburette.

The desired ionic strength of the solution was maintained by the addition of appropriate amount of 2M sodium perchlorate solution. Care was taken to get the required ratio of dioxane-water in the solutions used for measurement. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through an assembly containing the electrodes to keep away CO₂.

Calibration of glass electrode in different solvent mixtures was done by the experimental method outlined by Van Uitert and Haas⁸. The procedure as mentioned by these authors was used to convert pH meter readings i.e., B values in dioxane-water media into pH values.

Results and Discussions

For the calculations of stability constants of Cu(II) complexes it was assumed that factors like hydrolysis of Cu(II) ion and formation of polynuclear hydrogen and hydroxyl bearing complexes could be neglected on the following grounds:

(i) The pH of hydrolysis of Cu(II) ion obtained from the deviation of Cu(II) ion curve from the acid curve was around pH 5.5. The departure of the metal complex titration curve from the reagent curve was observed around pH 3.0.

(ii) The experimental solutions being very dilute, the probability of existence of polynuclear species under experimental conditions, if any, was not expected to be significant.

Determination of formation constants:

The proton-ligand formation number \bar{n}_A and the metal-ligand formation number \bar{n} were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's expression⁹. The values of pK

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and $\log K$ were calculated by following the point-wise method.

(a) The maximum value of \bar{n} at each ionic strength was around 0.9 before the pH of precipitation. This shows that 1:1 complex only formed before the commencement of hydrolysis. The values of pK_1 , pK_2 , and $\log K_1$ are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS IN THE MEDIA OF VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS

μ	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_1$
0.02	2.89	5.13	3.41
0.04	2.87	5.08	3.35
0.06	2.84	5.04	3.31
0.10	2.80	5.00	3.22
0.20	2.66	4.89	3.17
0.40	2.60	4.57	3.07
0.60	2.35	4.37	3.01
0.80	2.14	4.19	2.97
1.00	2.00	4.19	2.92

(b) The observed and thermodynamic values of pK and $\log K_1$ determined in 20%, 40%, 60%, and 80% dioxane-water (v/v) mixtures at 30° and 0.1M ionic strength are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS IN THE MEDIA OF VARIOUS WATER-DIOXANE MIXTURES

% Dioxane	pK_1		pK_2		$\log K_1$	
	Prac- tical	Thermo- dynamic	Prac- tical	Thermo- dynamic	Prac- tical	Thermo- dynamic
20	3.14	3.29	6.28	6.43	3.83	3.98
40	3.60	3.94	7.04	7.38	4.74	5.08
60	4.10	4.99	7.65	8.54	5.28	6.17
80	4.53	6.93	8.37	10.77	6.23	8.63

Influence of ionic strengths :

It may be seen from the data of Table 1, that increase in ionic strength decreased the values of pK_1 , pK_2 , and $\log K_1$. The data was analysed by Brönsted equation :

$$\log K = \log K^0 + A\Delta Z^2\sqrt{\mu} \quad \dots (1)$$

where A is the Debye-Hückel constant, ΔZ^2 is the difference in the square of the charges of product and reactant ions and K^0 is the formation constant at zero ionic strength. The values of pK_1 , pK_2 , and $\log K_1$ were plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$ (Fig. 1).

It may be noted from these plots that at higher values of μ , the points do not lie on a single straight line indicating thereby the non-applicability of Brönsted equation at higher values of μ . However a straight line can be drawn through the first four or five point.

Fig. 1. Plots of pK or $\log K_1$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$

alongwith the expected ones for different probable reactions are as follows :

Reaction	ΔZ^2 from slope values	
	Expected	Observed
$H_2L \xrightleftharpoons{pK_1} HL^- + H^+$	+1.0	+0.7
$HL^- \xrightleftharpoons{pK_2} L^{2-} + H^+$	+2.1	+0.8
$Cu^{2+} + HL^- \xrightleftharpoons{\log K_1} CuL + H^+$	-2.1	-1.3

The slope values observed in all cases are less than the expected values. They do not give conclusive evidence regarding the magnitude of the charges of the reacting species but merely indicate that the reacting species are oppositely charged.

The nonapplicability of equation (1) is expected in view of the limitations of the Debye-Hückel limiting law which is generally applicable to electrolytes only below 0.1M ionic strength. The modified form of the Debye-Hückel equation when applied to this system gave the slope values +0.8, +1.5 and -1.1 for pK_1 , pK_2 , and $\log K_1$ respectively which are not satisfactory.

Scatchard¹¹ made a further modification of the Debye-Hückel equation by introducing a factor representing the size of the ions and this modification when introduced into the Brönsted-Christian¹¹ equation gave the relation

$$\log K = \log K^0 + \frac{A\Delta Z^2\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + B a \sqrt{\mu}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where A and B are Debye-Hückel constant and 'a' is an ionic interaction parameter. The computation of 'a' was done by observing the influence of different values of 'a' on the constancy of equation (2). The accurate value of 'a' can be calculated by a trial method by successively putting different values of 'a' in the equation and observing its influence on the log K⁰ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plots. It is expected that for a correct value of 'a' log K⁰ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot should be linear and parallel to $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. Fig. 2(a), (b) and (c) represents log K₁⁰ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plots with 'a' values 4Å, 5Å, and 6Å. These calculations were made taking the values of A and B as 0.5161 and 0.3301 × 10⁸ in water at 30°.¹²

Fig. 2. Plots of log K₁⁰ against $\sqrt{\mu}$

It may be observed from Fig. 2 that out of three plots only one corresponding to a = 6Å is parallel to $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. Taking this value of 'a' the variation of log K₁ vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+1.98\sqrt{\mu}}$ was studied. It is seen from the Fig. 3. that a linear relation over an entire range of ionic strengths is observed for Cu(II)-phthalic acid system. The observed linearity is much better than given by log K₁ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ or log K₁ vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$ plots.

The plot gives a value of -2.0 for $\Delta\Delta Z^2$. This value suggests that the reaction is occurring between oppositely charged species and it should be represented as

which supports earlier conclusions.

Cu(II)-phthalic acid system can be further investigated in greater detail by following the said mechanism. The thermodynamic stability constant K₁⁰ at zero ionic strength for the reaction, considering the

recently modified Davies¹³ equation is given by

$$\log K_1 = \log K_1^0 - \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\} \Delta\Delta Z^2.$$

Fig. 3. Plot of log K₁ against $\left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+1.98\sqrt{\mu}} \right\}$

Fig. 4 representing the plot of

$$\log K_1 \text{ vs } \left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\}$$

shows that all the points in the range of 0.02M to 0.4M fall on a straight line giving a slope value -2.02. The slope value expected from the reaction between Cu²⁺ and phthalic acid is -2.06, which is in very good agreement with the observed value. It may, therefore, be inferred that the reaction follows the assumed mechanism and there is no possibility of complexes of the type CuHL being formed. In such a situation the reaction would be represented as

and the expected slope value be -1.03.

Thermodynamic stability constants :

The thermodynamic constants at zero ionic strength obtained from various plots are listed below :

x-axis →	$\sqrt{\mu}$	$\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$	$\left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\}$	$\left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+Ba\sqrt{\mu}} \right\}$
y-axis ↓				
pK ₁ ⁰	3.01	3.08	—	—
pK ₂ ⁰	5.24	5.29	—	—
log K ₁ ⁰	3.52	3.54	3.58	3.62

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log K_1$ against $\left\{ \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.3\mu \right\}$

The thermodynamic constant obtained from a plot where the slope value is in agreement with the theoretical value is taken as the most accurate value. These values are given below :

$$\begin{aligned} pK_1^0 & 3.08 \\ pK_2^0 & 5.29 \\ \log K_1^0 & 3.62 \end{aligned}$$

The above discussion, therefore, leads to the conclusion that these complexes behave as ion-pairs in water. The $\log K_1$ for copper phthalate is of the same order as that of copper succinate which is 3.40¹⁴ and is less than for oxalate by one unit. Davies¹⁴ has compared $\log K_1$ values for sulphates, malonates and succinates of Cu(II) and Ni(II) and has remarked that a rigid distinction between electrostatic ion-pairs and complexes is hard to maintain. It may, therefore, be inferred that these complexes are ionic in nature.

The average distance of closest approach would be greater than the sum of the crystallographic radii of the bare ions, though not necessarily inclusive of the thickness of a whole number of layers of water molecules surrounding the ions. The difference

between the radius sum and 'a' is greater for strongly hydrated than for weakly hydrated ions. Davies has presented values of 'a' for a number of ion-pairs like Cu(II)-malonate and Ba(II)- and Zn(II)-oxalates¹⁴. The 'a' values for 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 electrolytes are 3.5 and 6.2 Å¹⁵. The 'a' value observed in the present investigation is 6 Å thereby showing that the complex is of 2 : 1 type.

Influence of dielectric constants :

It is seen from Table 2 that pK_1 , pK_2 , and $\log K_1$ values increase with percentage increase of dioxane in the mixture as is well known.

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